

ADVAGEN

DELIVERABLE REPORT

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Development of ADVanced next GENeration Solid-State batteries for Electromobility Applications

GA n° 101069743

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DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	

Dissemination Level		
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SEN	Sensitive	

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Project summary

This report is part of the deliverables from the project "ADVAGEN" (Development of ADVANCED next GENERATION Solid-State batteries for Electromobility Applications), which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101069743.

To date, the battery market is dominated by lithium-ion (Li-ion) chemistries, as the energy density has more than doubled and their costs have dropped by a factor of at least 10. However, conventional Li-ion batteries (LIB) are reaching their performance limits in terms of energy density and facing safety issues, therefore the development and production of new battery generations, such as Solid-State Batteries (SSBs) is required to create a new industry value chain in Europe towards their commercialization. Consequently, high-energy-density EU⁻¹ will ensure the supply of, among others, the automotive sector. To do so, the development and deployment of new manufacturing technologies, enabling the largescale production of SSBs, is crucial. Indeed, among the overarching themes to develop and produce sustainable batteries in the future, the BATTERY 2030+ roadmap⁴ considers manufacturability as a cross-cutting key area. Innovative and scalable manufacturing techniques to produce SSBs will accelerate cost reduction, energy savings, and enhanced safety. ADVAGEN will develop a new lithium metal () battery cell technology based on a safe, reliable, and high performing hybrid solid-state electrolyte (LLZO-LPS based), gaining a competitive advantage over the worldwide (mainly Asian) competition. This will sustainably strengthen the EU as a technological and manufacturing leader in batteries as specified in the ERTRAC electrification roadmap and SET-Plan Action Point-7^{OBJ}. ADVAGEN consortium contains key EU actors in the battery sector, from industrial materials producers (CPT) battery manufacturer (ABEE) to R&D centers (IKE, CEA, IREC, TUB, CICE, POLITO, INEGI, UL, FEV) and the automotive industry (TME), covering the complete knowledge and value chain. By developing high-performance, affordable and safe batteries, ADVAGEN aims to re-establish European competitiveness in battery cell production.

Objective and Executive summary

In order to maximise the visibility of the ADVAGEN project, as well as the wide promotion of its results, the partners have hereby drafted a plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (abbreviated as DEC plan in the following). This document will be the reference for ADVAGEN partners for planning the activities and evaluating the impact of communication and dissemination activities, as well as exploitation ones. Such a plan will be updated and adjusted as the project progresses. In particular, this deliverable (D8.4) is the update of D8.1 (M6) submitted and approved earlier, and D8.5 at M48 will be the final one. Yet, modifications can be carried out more regularly depending on the results of the initial communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

The main purpose of this DEC plan is to ensure that the project research and results are widely disseminated to the appropriate target audiences, at appropriate times along the project lifetime, via appropriate methods, and that those who can contribute to the development, evaluation, uptake, and

¹ https://setis.ec.europa.eu/implementing-actions/set-plan-documents_en

exploitation of the ADVAGEN project results can be identified and encouraged to interact with the project on a regular and systematic basis.

Furthermore, this document describes the methodology that will be used for the definition of the Exploitation plans for the KERs (T8.3) as well as the networking activities (T8.4). For the development of the Exploitation plans, as a first step, the KERs will be further elaborated during the project term. During the General Assembly (GA) meetings, TechConcepts has already organized two workshops, first for team building while the second for the identification of unforeseen KERs and classification of all the KERs. Such classifications includes further detailing of the foreseen and unforeseen KERs, including the identification of the exploitation potential of each KER (scientific, societal, commercial and/or regulatory). Finally, this document will provide an update of the networking and clustering activities carried out within the project so far.

List of partners

N°	Name	Short name	Country
1	AVESTA BATTERY & ENERGY ENGINEERING	ABEE	BE
2	INEGI - INSTITUTO DE CIENCIA E INOVACAO EM ENGENHARIA MECANICA E ENGENHARIA INDUSTRIAL	INEGI	PT
3	POLITECNICO DI TORINO	POLITO	IT
4	FEV EUROPE GMBH	FEV	DE
5	COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVE	CEA	FR
6	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG	TUBS	DE
7	CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA DE ENERGIAS ALTERNATIVAS FUNDACION, CIC ENERGIGUNE FUNDAZIOA	CICE	ES
8	FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	IREC-CERCA	ES
9	TOYOTA MOTOR EUROPE NV	TME	BE
10	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJAN	UL	SI
11	EUROQUALITY SARL	EQY	FR
12	TECHCONCEPTS BV	TC	NL
13	CERAMIC POWDER TECHNOLOGY AS	CERPOTECH	NO
14	IKERLAN S. COOP	IKERLAN	ES

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List of Abbreviations

Ah: Ampere-hour

DEC plan: Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

NMC: Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide

SAG: Stakeholder Advisory group

TRL: Technology Readiness Level

Introduction

As the success of the ADVAGEN project is strongly dependent on well-coordinated communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, the partners have included a specific work package for this purpose, i.e., WP8 “Communication, dissemination, exploitation and networking activities” led by Euroquality (EQY).

On the one hand, dissemination activities are designed to reach a wide range of stakeholders, from the academic world and industrial sector to potential investors and policymakers, to foster the valorisation of project results. On the other hand, communication activities will raise awareness about the project's existence and the global challenges it tackles by targeting the large public. For all these activities, the ADVAGEN partners must develop communication and dissemination materials adapted to the interests of each target group and deliver the appropriate messages for maximising the impacts for the project.

The plan for dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities drafted hereafter, defines the targeted audiences, the means, tools and channels to reach them, the key messages to be conveyed, the schedule and complementarity of the activities, and the measures to assess the success of these activities. This document also addresses the confidentiality issues related to communication and dissemination of project information. This will enable ADVAGEN to achieve its communication and dissemination objectives, in particular: i) the identification of the main concerned stakeholders; ii) raising awareness of the target audiences, mainly through the project's results and benefits; iii) fostering collaborations with stakeholders and the research community for sharing resources, achieve synergies and exchange information and knowledge; iv) promoting the results of the project for TRL increase.

1. Guidelines for all dissemination and communication activities

At the beginning of the project, the visual identity of the project was elaborated. This includes a graphic charter, a project logo, and templates for documents (presentations, deliverables etc.) to ensure visibility and recognition of the ADVAGEN public image. The graphic charter of the ADVAGEN project is available in **Annex 1**, and it also provides an overview of the templates that have been developed. The deliverable template is the one used for this deliverable. All documents have already been made available to the ADVAGEN consortium (on the secure project shared folder). They will serve as a basis for partners to

advertise the project and perform dissemination and communication activities, both within their institutions and during events.

Furthermore, when carrying out dissemination and/or communication activities about the project, partners will also mention the following:

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2. Strategy for dissemination

As a reminder, *dissemination* stands for the public disclosure of the project's results, right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way to enable them to use the results in their own work. The stakeholder groups include e.g. research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers, etc.

In ADVAGEN, dissemination activities will aim to create a relevant follower stakeholder community to spread information on the project and its results in a second phase. This follower stakeholder community will combine all profiles of the target audience described in section 1.1.

2.1 Targeted stakeholders

The target audiences for ADVAGEN dissemination cover a wide range of stakeholders, from the academic world and industrial sector to policymakers. The targets have been gathered together with dissemination targets in Table 1.

Table 1: Targeted stakeholder categories in ADVAGEN

Stakeholder	Scope
Scientific community, including other research projects	<p>Field of solid-state batteries in general, with in particular the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electrolytes; - Anodes and protection layers; - Nickel rich cathodes; - Stable and performant large-scale pouch cells; - Operando characterisation techniques ; - Thermomechanical integration ; - Environmental sustainability; - Recycling process. <p>Identified other projects (e.g. Horizon Europe ones) with which collaboration and dissemination will be envisioned will be detailed in Table 2.</p>

<p>Industry</p>	<p>Battery industry in general, with battery manufacturers and battery materials producers. In particular, ADVAGEN partners have already identified at this stage 3 key exploitation sectors, in which the developed solid-state battery in ADVAGEN could be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automotive Sector; - Energy Sector ; - Electromobility Sector. <p>Identified industry clusters with which collaboration and dissemination will be envisioned will be detailed in Table 3.</p>
<p>Policy makers</p>	<p>Influence stakeholders and public bodies in charge of energy at national and EU levels. Identified policy makers with which dissemination will be envisioned will be detailed in Table 3.</p>

2.2 Key messages per target audience

To date, the battery market is dominated by lithium-ion (Li-ion) chemistries. However, conventional Li-ion batteries are reaching their performance limits in terms of energy density and facing safety issues, and the development and production of new battery generations is required, such as solid-state batteries. To do so, developing and deploying new manufacturing technologies, enabling the large-scale production of solid-state batteries, is crucial.

The main key message of ADVAGEN is: **“ADVAGEN will [targeted message to specific target groups – see below].”**

This key message will be sent to the different target audiences at appropriate precision levels and be supported by other messages, detailed in the following.

Scientific community

The key message towards the scientific community is: **“ADVAGEN will develop, manufacture and validate the most performing, stable, low-cost and safe solid-state large pouch cells (10Ah), with optimal environmental performance.”**

This message will also be completed with the following elements, possibly developed with precise project content and results: “To do so, the partners will develop an innovative hybrid oxide-sulfide ceramic electrolyte to be integrated with a novel Li metal anode, and a high nickel rich NMC-based and/or lithium nickel oxide-based cathode. Furthermore, a sulfide-based catholyte may be added. The development of the hybrid electrolyte cells will include eco-design principles, in order to reduce costs and mitigate potential environmental impacts throughout the life cycle of the ADVAGEN battery solution.”

Special collaboration is planned with other national and European projects, as listed in Table 2 (non-exhaustive list).

Table 2: Projects with which collaboration is envisaged

Project	Description and link with ADVAGEN
LISA H2020 2019-2022	<p><u>Objective:</u> Optimizing Li-S components and battery cells for automotive integration</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Integration of solid-state electrolytes, also sulfides, into large cell battery production line. Application of thin film protective layers in Li-electrolyte interface</p>
FESTBATT German gov. 2019-2022	<p><u>Objective:</u> Cluster of Competence for solid-state batteries</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> The aim of "FestBatt" is to produce and upscale suitable solid electrolytes in order to create the basis for the evaluation of the new materials by industry and application-oriented institutes</p>
3BELIEVE H2020 2020-2023	<p><u>Objective:</u> Development of proper coating solutions for cathodes to improve lifetime</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Applying of suitable coating solutions with low interface resistance</p>
Safelimove H2020 2020-2023	<p><u>Objective:</u> Development and prototyping of oxide based solid state battery cells</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Optimisation of interfaces, advanced modelling to predict battery behaviour and coating of lithium</p>
Sublime H2020 2020-2024	<p><u>Objective:</u> Development and prototyping sulfide based solid state battery cells</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Development and prototyping of oxide based solid state battery cells</p>
COBRA H2020 2020-2023	<p><u>Objective:</u> Develop a novel Co-free Li-ion battery technology for a light electric vehicle with superior energy density than current batteries at lower cost.</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Material development, cell testing, post-mortem analysis towards a high-energy and cost-effective Li-ion battery</p>
SPINMATE HEU 2022-2026	<p><u>Objective:</u> Demonstrate a scalable, sustainable, safe and cost-effective digital-driven proof-of-concept pilot line, at a TRL6 level, as a first step towards the large-scale manufacturing of generation 4b (Gen 4b) SSB cells and module to support the electrification of the automotive sector</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Cell testing, SSB development</p>
SOLiD HEU 2022-2026	<p><u>Objective:</u> Sustainable and cost-efficient pilot-scale manufacturing process. It will use roll-to-roll (R2R) dry extrusion coating for the blend of cathode active material, solid polymer electrolyte, and conducting additives</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Material and cell development</p>
PULSELION HEU 2022-2026	<p><u>Objective:</u> Develop the manufacturing technology for Generation 4b solid-state batteries composed of a lithium-metal anode, sulfide solid electrolytes and a nickel-rich nickel–manganese–cobalt cathode. A novel pulsed laser deposition technique will be adapted and modified into a single-step vacuum process for safe and efficient manufacturing of the batteries' anode components.</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Material development (especially the anode), cell testing</p>
HELENA HEU 2022-2026	<p><u>Objective:</u> Develop a high-capacity Ni-rich cathode (NMC), high-energy Li metal (LiM) anode and Li-ion superionic halide solid electrolyte for application in electric vehicles and especially in aircrafts.</p> <p><u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Material development (especially the anode), cell testing</p>
SEATBELT HEU 2022-2026	<p><u>Objective:</u> Cells produced by low-cost solvent-free extrusion process comprising a combination of innovative materials: Li metal, hybrid polymer electrolyte, safe cathode active material.</p>

	<u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Material development (especially the anode), cell testing, recycling process
AM4BAT HEU 2022-2026	<u>Objective:</u> Manufacture an anode-free all-solid-state battery using a cost-competitive and sustainable photopolymerization 3D printing process. Developed materials include: i) single crystal NMC811 with superior energy, ii) LNMO Co-free and higher voltage for power AM4BAT variant, iii) doped LLZO with different size for higher loading, and iv) novel acrylic, nanocellulose, sustainable photocurable polymer. <u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Cathode development, cell testing
PSIONIC HEU 2022-2026	<u>Objective:</u> Employ amorphous cross-linked polyethylene oxide laminated on a thin lithium foil at the anode and high voltage cathode coated with a single-ion conductive polymer. Use of the manufacturing technology available to BlueSolutions. <u>Link with ADVAGEN:</u> Material development (especially the anode), cell testing

Industry

The key message towards the industry is: **“ADVAGEN will reduce the battery pack cost, increase the battery lifetime and its technical performance proving the potential growth of EU cell manufacturing industry .”**

This message will also be completed with the following elements, possibly developed with precise project content and results: “To do so, the partners will develop an innovative hybrid oxide-sulfide ceramic electrolyte to be integrated with a novel Li metal anode, and a high nickel rich NMC-based and/or lithium nickel oxide-based cathode. Based on these, ADVAGEN will demonstrate the most performing, stable, low-cost and safe solid-state large pouch cells (10Ah) and will integrate them in a 48V battery module.”

Table 3: Industry clusters with which collaboration is envisaged (non-exhaustive)

Industry cluster
Advanced Materials Cluster (MAV) from the Agency for Business Competitiveness at Catalonia
CFI - Ceramic forum international
Refractories WORLDFORUM
EARPA - Association of automotive R&D organisations
EMIRI - The Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative
EUCAR - European Council for Automotive R&D
LIPLANET

Polymakers

The key message towards the policymakers and influence actors is: **“ADVAGEN will adopt new procedures and standards towards the next-generation solid-state cells and novel development policies including modeling and simulation which will reduce R&D time and costs, as well as potentiate the decarbonisation of the transport sector.”**

This message will also be completed with the following elements, possibly developed with precise project content and results: “ADVAGEN enters into EU targets for 90 % reduction of GHG emissions by 2050 compared to 1990 for the transport sector².”

Table 4: Policy makers/influence actors with which collaboration is envisaged (non-exhaustive)

Policy makers and influence actors
Bureau of European Policy Advisers
The Batteries European Partnership Association
Influence actors of the European Battery Alliance
BATTERYPLAT (Spain)
Ministry of research in all ADVAGEN partners’ countries (e.g. BMBF in Germany)
Ministry of economic affairs/energy in all ADVAGEN partners’ countries (e.g. BMWi in Germany)

2.3 Channels for dissemination

Both physical and digital channels will be used for dissemination, and include the following:

- Scientific publications, mainly targeting the scientific community;
- Attendance and organisation of conferences, workshops and events, targeting all stakeholder audiences - the scientific community, the industry, policy makers;
- Links to existing initiatives, mainly targeting the scientific community;
- Creation of a Stakeholder Advisory Group (SAG), mainly targeting the industry.

Table 5 summarises the key performance indicators for each of these activities, which are detailed in the following.

Table 5: Quantification of ADVAGEN dissemination activities

Dissemination measure	Purpose	Key performance indicators	Targeted Audience
Open access scientific publications	Research	≥ 5	Scientific community
Organisation of workshops	Knowledge exchange	≥ 1 workshop/year	Electric vehicle and battery community coming from scientific community, industry, policy makers
Participation in outreach events (e.g. conferences)	Knowledge exchange	> 20	Energy, battery and electric vehicle community, coming from scientific community, industry, policy makers

² Transport and environment report 2021 Decarbonising road transport — the role of vehicles, fuels and transport demand. EEA Report, 02/2022

Links to existing national and/or European initiatives	Knowledge and good practices exchange	> 5	Scientific community
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Scientific publications

At least **5-10 open-access papers** will be published during the project, mainly targeting the scientific community on solid-state batteries. The type of publication and the targeted journals are detailed Table 6.

Table 6: Scientific publications foreseen in the ADVAGEN project

Partners	Type and number of publications targeted and journals
ABEE	Number of publications: 1-2 Subjects: Battery cells production and upscaling Journals: Journal of Energy Storage, Applied Energy
POLITO	Number of publications: 2 Subjects: Aging behaviour and mechanisms, multiscale modeling Journals: Journal of Power Sources, Journal of Energy Storage, Applied Energy
FEV	Number of publications: 1-2 Subjects: Safety of next generation lithium-ion cells, Upscaling cell properties into battery packs Journals: Journal of Power Sources, Journal of Energy Storage, Applied Energy
TUBS	Number of publications: 3 Subjects: Conductivity of oxide-sulfide-hybrid electrolyte, Particle size ratio of solid electrolyte and active material in cathode, Influence of carbon black structure on the performance of the composite cathode Journals: MDPI Batteries, Journal of the Electrochemical Society, Journal of Power Sources
CICE	Number of publications: 2 Subjects: Hybrid oxide-sulphide electrolyte for SSBs, electrochemically stable cathode in combination with sulphides Journals: Advanced Energy Materials, Chemistry of Materials, Journal of Power Source
IREC	Number of publications: 3 Subjects: NMC cathode development, operando characterization methods, Ageing mechanism and post-mortem analysis. Journals: Advanced Energy Materials, Journal of Materials Chemistry A, Journal of Power Source
INEGI	Number of publications: 2 Subjects: SSB Sustainability Journals: Journal cleaner production; Journal of resources, conservation and recycling
UL	Number of publications: 3 Subjects: Detailed mesoscopic model of a secondary electrode particle with surrounding solid-state electrolyte, Advanced multi-scale model of the elementary solid-state electrochemical cell, Model-based characterisation of the intra-solid-state-battery phenomena based on the EIS approach Journals: Journal of The Electrochemical Society, Journal of Power Sources

Attendance and organisation of conferences, workshops and events

At least **4 workshops** (1 per year of the project) are expected to be organised by ADVAGEN partners. These will focus on sharing and discussing ADVAGEN's results. In particular, the final event organised is expected to focus on scientific and technological advances made by the project, also covering future expectations and exploitation strategies.

Furthermore, at least **20 outreach events** are expected to be attended by the project partners during the lifetime of the project. A preliminary list of events which partners may attend is presented in Table 7. This list will be enriched during the lifetime of the project.

These include workshops, seminars, conferences, side events, etc., on topics related to:

- Energy;
- Battery, and solid-state batteries in particular;
- The electric vehicle community;
- Standardisation.

For partners to efficiently present ADVAGEN during such events, dedicated guidelines and presentation materials have been already detailed in section 1.

Table 7: Foreseen outreach events attended by ADVAGEN partners

Date	Event name	Location
April 2023 / annual	Kraftwerk Batterie - Advanced Battery Power	Aachen, Germany
May 2023 / annual	Battery2030+	Uppsala, Sweden
June 2023/ annual	EUROBAT General Assembly and Forum	Madrid, Spain
August 2023 / annual	Solid-state Battery Summit	Chicago, USA & online
August 2023 / annual	ICLB - International conference of Li ion batteries	17 th in Vancouver, Canada
September 2023	Battery Tech	Munich, Germany
September 2023 / annual	GEI - Giornate dell'Elettrochimica Italiana (Days of the Italian Electrochemistry)	Palermo, Italy
October 2023	244 th ECS meeting	Gothenburg, Sweden
November 2023 / annual	International Battery Production Conference	Braunschweig, Germany
December 2023 / annual	International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment and Urban Sustainability - ICLCAUS	Barcelona, Spain
December 2023/ annual	AABC Advanced Automotive Battery Conference	23 rd in San Diego, USA
June 2024	CIRP LCE - Life Cycle Engineering Conference	31 st in Turin, Italy
June 2024 / every 2 years	IMLB - International Meeting on Lithium Batteries	Stuttgart, Germany
July 2024	24 th International Conference on Solid State Ionics	London, UK
Several networking events / year	EMIRI - The Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative network	Online

To be determined	Nanofoundry and Fine Analysis Europe research infrastructure The mission NFFA.eu	Across Europe
To be determined	European Battery Alliance250 workshop	To be determined
To be determined	BEPA - The Batteries European Partnership Association events	To be determined

Links to existing initiatives

c.f. Table 2 for the targeted initiatives with which collaboration is envisaged. Furthermore, partners of the ADVAGEN project foresee that at least **5 collaborations** in the field of solid-state batteries will be established during the project’s lifetime.

Participation in the Solid4B cluster

The creation of a cluster, namely the Solid4b cluster, at M9, is a great opportunity for dissemination activities. ADVAGEN and other EU projects (AM4BAT, HIDDEN, PULSELION, SEATBELT, SOLiD, SPINMATE, PSIONIC) have been invited to this cluster to participate in different events (e.g. webinars and workshops) to exchange on different topics related to solid-state batteries. Such large clustering activities gather a very wide audience and relevant stakeholders interested by the results of ADVAGEN. ADVAGEN partners will have the opportunity to disseminate project’s challenges and achievements in these events.

ADVAGEN will actively take part to upcoming Solid4B cluster events such as the hybrid event covering the pilot line challenges faced under the umbrella of EU projects, in April 2024. As well as events organised by members of the cluster such as the AM4BAT’s hybrid workshop on “Stakeholders Engagement”, in February 2024. Overall, this cluster will allow to disseminate ADVAGEN’s insights and results in **>2 events per year**.

Creation of a Stakeholder Advisory Group

ADVAGEN partners have created a Stakeholder Advisory Group (SAG), with privileged access to the results of the ADVAGEN project, for gathering advise and guidelines (e.g. industrial ones) for guiding the developments in ADVAGEN. In particular, members of the SAG will be invited to the workshops organised by ADVAGEN partners. Members considered are mainly industrial ones (c.f. Table 3), yet relevant research-oriented organisations focused on solid-state batteries will be invited. To date, 5 different organisations have joined the SAG (2 industrial organisations, 3 research-oriented ones). Partners of ADVAGEN target to have at least **5 members in the SAG by M24**, which is already reached by M18.

Table 8: SAG members

Name	Organisation	Position/Activities
Daniela Fontana	COMAU	Battery global competence center
Maria Helena Braga	University of Porto	Associate professor at the Engineering Physics Department
Martijn Stamm	EARPA - Association of Automotive R&D organizations	Executive Board member EARPA, Market director TNO
Miran Gaberšček	National Institute of Chemistry	Department of Materials Chemistry (Head), Laboratory for Electrocatalysis (Researchers)

Dr. Florian Strauss	The Research University in the Helmholtz Association	Group Leader - Tailored Electrolytes for Lithium Solid-State Batteries
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3. Strategy for communication

As a reminder, *communication* aims at promoting the project and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the press and media, and the large public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and to some specific audiences while demonstrating how European funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

3.1 Key message

The key message towards the general public is: **“ADVAGEN will improve solid-state batteries production processes, equipment, and pilot line production, to advance the manufacturability of solid-state batteries in the European industry for application in e.g. the transport sector. Moreover, it will contribute to establishing a new manufacturing industry in Europe, which means countless jobs and opportunities will be created.”**

3.2 Channels for communication

Both physical and digital channels will be used for communication, and include the following:

- Online publishing (popular science articles, newsletters, etc.);
- Creation and maintenance of a project’s website;
- Creation and maintenance of project’s social media accounts;
- Creation of promotional material, and a project video.

Table 99 summarises the key performance indicators for each of these activities, which are detailed in the following.

Table 9: Quantification of ADVAGEN communication activities, targeting the general public

Dissemination measure	Key performance indicators
Online publishing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 7 newsletters (half-yearly) > 4 popular science articles > 500 readings per popular science article
ADVAGEN website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 300 views/month ≥ 8 updates/year
ADVAGEN social media	> 20 posts/year

	<p>> 500 views/post</p> <p>> 250 followers or subscribers on all social media at the end of the project</p>
Promotional material	<p>> 500 leaflet or brochure distribution</p> <p>> 2,500 views of the project video at the end of the project</p>

Online publishing

At least **5-10 open-access papers** will be published during the project, mainly targeting the scientific community on solid-state batteries. The type of publication and the targeted journals are detailed Table 6.

Creation and maintenance of a project’s website

A dedicated website has been created (<https://www.advagen.eu/>; Figure 1). It is already available in English and will be updated throughout the project by ABEE in order to enhance visibility and communicate on the project. This live website was created to share information, news, publications etc. during the project duration as well as six years after the end of the project. The main purpose of creating the website is not only to make available public results and interesting news about the project but also to provide an environment for e-collaboration within ADVAGEN consortium. Importantly, it will also enhance the visibility/the socio-economic impact of the project as well as involve the stakeholders in every phase of the project and ensure interaction with the community outside the project. Certain materials developed for physical dissemination (i.e. leaflets, videos, infographics) will also be accessible in the “news” section of the website. Statistical data will be gathered about the website visitors, the number of clicks, countries etc. This data will be analysed by Google Analytics software and included in the project reports. The website will be responsive to work on various devices and screen sizes, for instance smartphones.

Partners aim at having > **300 views of the website/month**, and having \geq **8 updates/year**.

Figure 1: Homepage of the ADVAGEN website at the time of submission of the D8.4 deliverable

Creation and maintenance of project's social media accounts

Two social media accounts have been created for the ADVAGEN project:

- On LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/he-advagen/>
- On Twitter: <https://twitter.com/HEAdvagen>

Relevant information will be shared across both project social media accounts throughout the project. The illustrations below show headers of LinkedIn (Figure 2) and Twitter pages (Figure 3).

Figure 2: ADVAGEN LinkedIn header – January 2024

Figure 3: ADVAGEN Twitter header – January 2024

Regular posts will be made by EQY on news related to project progress (milestones, developments, newsletter, etc.), events (reports, forthcoming conferences, organised workshops, etc.), related research and developments (non-exhaustive list). Foreseen key social media campaigns along ADVAGEN’s lifetime are detailed in Table 1010.

Table 10: Foreseen key social media campaigns in ADVAGEN, and associated timing

Foreseen date	Topic	Partners involved	Communication support
September 2022	Launch of the ADVAGEN project and first press release	All	Written presentation & press release
November 2022 – March 2023	Presentation of ADVAGEN partners	All	Written presentations & photos
April 2023 – September 2023	General concept presentation	NA	Written posts & animated video
October 2023 – December 2023	SOLID4B clustering communication	All	Written posts/reposts & emphasise on ADVAGEN partners’ participation
January 2024 - February 2024	Detailed concept presentation	All	Written presentations, interviews if relevant & infographics
March 2024 – September 2024	Work packages presentation	All (especially work package leaders)	Written presentations, interviews if relevant & infographics
October 2024 – September 2025	Presentation of ADVAGEN’s first results	All	Written presentations, interviews if relevant & infographics & photos

October 2025 – February 2026	SAG presentation	SAG members	Written presentations & photos
March 2026 – July 2026	Final results presentation	All	Written presentations, interviews if relevant & infographics & photos

Partners aim at having **> 20 posts/year**, **> 500 views/post**, and **> 250 followers** or subscribers on social media at the end of the project. All partners of the ADVAGEN project are of course invited to relay the information of ADVAGEN’s social media on their respective organisational accounts.

As a result of this communication activities until M18, the LinkedIn account as reached 329 followers. Newsletters and the project video convey more information about the ADVAGEN project than other post (e.g. with targeted content, reposts, etc.) and they have reached good performances. Newsletters published has reached around 200 impressions and the project video has reached over 1400 impressions and has been seen (on LinkedIn only) more than 630 times.

At M18, results of the communication to the general public on Twitter has not reached its objectives. Furthermore, since Twitter has been purchased and the name has been changed to “X” this social media seems to be less adapted to this kind of communication. Indeed, with the implementation of a paying system to promote the communication content, large European project struggles to reach their audience. As evidence, SPINMATE, ADVAGEN, PULSELION have only around 50 followers gathering mainly other EU/international projects which already have access to posted content on LinkedIn, and which does not represent the general public targeted. Hence, it has been decided to suppress the X account of the project. The LinkedIn account will be continued, and the same indicators will be maintained.

Creation of promotional material, and a project video

In order to promote the project during conferences and events, promotional material will be developed whenever needed by ADVAGEN partners. Such material will provide general information and technical and non-technical preliminary public results. It will consist of a leaflet (one release when ADVAGEN partners plan to attend first conferences, and one at the end of the project), a roll-up and a promotional document for potential customers or end-users. All the printouts will be uploaded to the ADVAGEN website in electronic format and will be available for downloading, and the printable versions will be uploaded in the secure shared folder accessible to all ADVAGEN partners. Finally, an animated project video will be created, presenting the project’s objectives, outcomes, etc. Partners aim at having **> 500 leaflet** or brochure distribution and **> 2,500 views of the project video** at the end of the project.

4. Strategy for exploitation and networking opportunities

Exploitation of the project results requires the development of an appropriate strategy to ensure the afterlife of the project. The following needs to be detailed:

- Project results that can be exploited;

- Which partners will be responsible for the exploitation of each project result, and of the overall technology proposed;
- End-users of the technology;
- The steps required to reach TRL9, as ADVAGEN is expected to reach TRL5 at its end.

To start with, partners of the ADVAGEN project have identified seven project results, detailed in **Error! Reference source not found.** Henceforth, called as KER and within the context of the project they have been treated as Foreseen KERs. For each have been identified the responsible partner(s), as well as the foreseen exploitation measures. End-users have been gathered in Table 3. The steps to reach TRL9 will be gathered in 7 project results (c.f.**Error! Reference source not found.**) as part of the plan to market, at a later stage of the project.

Such a path towards TRL9 and the market will be drafted by POLITO in T5.5. Recommendations about performances, aging and safety will be collected in order to define a roadmap putting together a list of parameters and properties necessary to lead this technology towards higher TRL. TC with support from all partners, and especially ABEE and EQY, will ensure the best valorisation of the project’s results after the end of the project by writing an exploitation plan (D8.3, M48). This plan will also include IPR aspects, with discussions on additional agreements to be foreseen in order to reach consent around the commercial exploitation of research outputs. An exploitation workshop summarizing all these aspects will be organised at the end of the project.

Table 11: Identified ADVAGEN project results

PR1: Hybrid solid electrolyte
<p><u>Concrete exploitation measures:</u> Offering engineering services to material suppliers, OEMs that are active in battery cell production, cell manufacturers and Through licensing of the manufacturing technology of solid-state batteries with hybrid solid state electrolyte and the recycling process flowchart.</p> <p><u>Associated management of intellectual property:</u> Patenting, licensing</p> <p><u>Responsible partners:</u> TUBS, CEA, CICE and ABEE</p>
PR2: Catholyte layer with hybrid solid electrolyte
<p><u>Concrete exploitation measures:</u> Offering engineering services to cell manufacturers and OEMs that are active in cell production. Transfer of the knowledge for future battery technologies beyond solid state technology.</p> <p><u>Associated management of intellectual property:</u> Patenting (only if innovative coating solutions are applied), licensing</p> <p><u>Responsible partners:</u> IREC, CPT , TUBS and ABEE</p>
PR3: Electrochemically stable thin film Li anode

<p><u>Concrete exploitation measures:</u> Knowledge acquired for future research projects, transfer to PhD students. Offering of engineering services for battery cell manufacturers and OEMs. Commercial Li metal electrode to wide range of industries (by ABEE).</p> <p><u>Associated management of intellectual property:</u> Publication, patenting, licensing</p> <p><u>Responsible partners:</u> ABEE and CICE</p>
<p>PR4: Solid state cell with hybrid solid state electrolyte</p>
<p><u>Concrete exploitation measures:</u> Carry over of project results into engineering work, product development, company internal workshops, knowledge transfer to PhD students at FEV; marketing to service providers for prototyping such solid-state batteries and recycling activity.</p> <p><u>Associated management of intellectual property:</u> Patenting</p> <p><u>Responsible partners:</u> ABEE and TUBS</p>
<p>PR5: New combined operando techniques</p>
<p><u>Concrete exploitation measures:</u> Offering engineering and subcontracting services to universities, RTO's, material developers and cell manufacturers.</p> <p><u>Associated management of intellectual property:</u> Patenting</p> <p><u>Responsible partners:</u> IREC, CICE and CEA</p>
<p>PR6: New recycling approach</p>
<p><u>Concrete exploitation measures:</u> Translate most relevant project results into scientific publications, knowledge acquired used in future projects and transferred to PhD students and young researchers.</p> <p><u>Associated management of intellectual property:</u> Open source publications, patenting, licensing</p> <p><u>Responsible partners:</u> ABEE and INEGI</p>
<p>PR7: Plan to market</p>
<p><u>Concrete exploitation measures:</u> Engineering services in terms of market studies, roadmaps.</p> <p><u>Associated management of intellectual property:</u> Market studies, roadmaps</p> <p><u>Responsible partners:</u> POLITO will lead the task of developing a roadmap to higher TRL. ABEE will support with the definition of the roadmap regarding manufacturing of the large battery cells and lithium metal electrodes. IREC will support from the interface technologies and challenges point of view. CEA will support from cell safety testing and material upscaling. TC will support all partners by leading the networking activities. A detailed plan and strategy, built in collaboration with relevant Stakeholders, as mentioned above and all the project partners will enable bringing the ADVAGEN technology to market quickly.</p>

Exploitation strategies as well as networking opportunities pertains to T8.3 and T8.4 respectively. Both these tasks are led by TC, and duely supported by EQY and ABEE. Furthermore, interaction of these 2 task with other relevant project tasks is presented hereunder.

Figure 3: Interactions between tasks of WP8.

This section is further divided into following sub-sections

- Team building workshops
- KER exploitation workshops
- Replacement of MI and next steps for collaboration
- Clustering activities as part of SOLID4B.

4.1 Team building workshops

As per the TC approach for maximizing project impact, *team building* within the consortium is a first step towards a successful exploitation of the project. TC has so far carried out 2 workshops (during the two GA meetings in Porto and Barcelona respectively). These workshops enable to get participants out of their comfort zone and their islanded approach, and facilitate networking and idea sharing in order to streamline exploitation of the project results.

During the M6 GA meeting in Porto (hosted in April 2023) the aim was to get to know each other and create an environment where people have associations to remember other participants by. TC hosted a simple game where participants were asked to introduce themselves, by mentioning what sets-them apart from the entire group. This uniqueness of each participant was a “association” that facilitated breaking the ice and people getting to know each other.

Figure 4: Picture of the introduction game hosted by TC at the GA meeting in Porto

During the M12 GA meeting in Barcelona (hosted in September 2023) the aim was to bring participants in teams and make them work together to understand how well they know the project – ADVAGEN, by setting up a simple quiz about the project.

Figure 5: Picture of the quiz hosted by TC in the GA meeting in Barcelona

4.2 KER exploitation workshops

For the development of the Exploitation plans and Business Models, a **4-step approach for effective exploitation of ADVAGEN results**, developed by TC, is followed. During this approach, inputs from the consortium partners will be collected in workshops (hosted during GAs) and in bilateral contacts. Technical innovations -KERS- are not realized within silo's but they are developed by partners (where clear ownership has to be defined); while relevant stakeholders will play a role in determining whether the innovations will be successful and widely adopted.

Figure 6: 4-step approach for effective exploitation of the ADVAGEN project results, developed by TC

In **step 1**, the KERS will be further elaborated during the first phase of the project execution. During the GA 1 meeting in Porto (April 2023) TechConcepts organized the 1st exploitation workshop to identify unforeseen KERS, while the second workshop in GA 2 meeting (September 2023) in Barcelona the KERS

were further detailed, including the identification of the exploitation potential of each KER (scientific, societal, commercial and/or regulatory). 7 foreseen KERs were identified during the proposal phase, while 11 new KERs have been identified during the 2 workshops hosted during the GA 1 and GA 2 so far.

Step 2 is an inside-out step. This step focuses on the definition of the KER ownership (with input from the IPR management task). In the 2nd step, single or joint foreground ownership is defined, the owner(s) that will exploit the KER will be identified, and the required background IPR from consortium member(s) or third parties is identified. This step was already carried out during the GA 2 meeting in Barcelona.

Results of the above 2 steps (highlighting the ownership and exploitation potential of the total 18 KERs) are presented in Appendix A – which is a sensitive attachment that includes stakeholder and KER exploitation potential information.

Remaining steps (3 and 4) will be carried out during the remaining project period.

Step 3 contains an outside-in approach, identifying the relevant stakeholders for the KERs, and their interest, needs and stakes. The stakeholders are mapped according to their interest and influence³, and the most relevant stakeholders for ADVAGEN KERs are defined. This step is undertaken in the 3rd exploitation workshop. This step will be carried out during the subsequent GA meetings.

Figure 7: TC approach for stakeholder mapping inspired by Hollman³

Then finally in **step 4**, the route to exploitation is elaborated in the form of an exploitation plan, resulting in an exploitation canvas.

³ Hollmann S, R. B. (2022). Ten simple rules on how to develop a stakeholder engagement plan. PLoS Comput Biol, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010520>

Figure 8: Format of the KER exploitation canvas developed by TechConcepts for Horizon Europe KER exploitation

As can be seen above, TC has already begin facilitating the exploitation plans for all the KERs (Foreseen as well as unforeseen). TC approach facilitates such process from the start of the project so that all the partners are taken step-by-step through the process and at the end of the project complete and comprehensive exploitation plans per KER are in place. Avoiding adhoc exploitation plan development is the basis of maximizing project impact.

4.3 Replacement of MI and next steps for collaboration

Efforts were made to connect with the Mission Innovation association (as part of task 8.4), but so far we have not been successful. Furthermore, the parent company of Toyota Motor Europe (TME) that is Toyota Motor Corporation is part of Mission Innovation and TME does not have a direct influence over MI. Due to this, it will not be possible for TME to set-up collaboration with MI. To overcome this, as a project we have identified an alternative association to replace MI.

The alternative association was identified during the exploitation workshop hosted by the leader of Exploitation (TechConcepts) during the GA2 in Barcelona. Before the GA, 4 replacement options were prepared in consultation with partners and during the GA a voting was carried out, with each beneficiary receiving 1 vote.

Process employed to identify a replacement

During the GA2, TechConcepts (partner leading the exploitation within ADVAGEN) carried out the second exploitation workshop and facilitated a voting session to identify a replacement for MI. 4 choices were on offer for the partners to choose from.

Table 12: Mission innovation replacement choices

Association	Which knowledge/expertise do this platform bring to the project
EUCAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to market and industry insights. • Regulatory Compliance • Communication and interaction with EU key stakeholders about project outcomes
ERTICO	Similar to EUCAR
UPCELL	Ecosystem of actors in the equipment and machinery for battery manufacturing industry stronger together
AGORIA	Digitalisation in industrial production, Technical regulations and standardisations

Each beneficiary had received 1 vote. The overview of the votes is hereunder

Figure 9: Overview of the vote for Mission Innovatin replacement

EUCAR was voted as the primary candidate for replacement. Justification for this choice is below.

- Previous positive experience during collaboration
- Direct point of contact, from the perspective of multiple partners and will help to realize a strong collaboration.
- Communicating and interaction with important stakeholders and creating awareness
- Have a strong Automotive sector expertise and comparable to MI - and can support for the plan to market.

UPCELL was voted as a runner up.

Next steps with respect to this collaboration are as follows:

- ADVAGEN will connect with EUCAR and solicit support with regards to plan to market and exploitation - as a direct replacement of MI.
- Secondly, ADVAGEN will make an effort to connect with UPCELL for inputs wrt upscaling of the innovations - this will be done by inviting UPCELL to the Advisory board.

With the above steps, ADVAGEN will ensure that this deviation eventually bring about positive opportunities to the project. We would also like to bring your attention to the attachment - where we have highlighted the detailed process about the voting process, the justification of the choice made and the perceived advantages for ADVAGEN.

4.4 Clustering activities as part of the SOLID4B cluster

Furthermore ADVAGEN is part of the SOLID4B cluster. Solid4B cluster works to enhance research synergies among the European-level projects working on solid state batteries, translating research data into valuable knowledge for diverse stakeholders. This cluster was built to synchronize and conjointly promote the R&D topics in the electric vehicle field. The knowledge and experience shared between different projects will support individual performance of the projects involved, while maximizing the dissemination range of achievements and respective impacts.

ADVAGEN has participated in 2 webinars hosted by the SOLID4B clusters. These dedicated workshops conducted by Solid4B cluster aim to discuss, promote, and disrupt ideas regarding safety, efficiency and sustainability of batteries and related e-mobility technologies by translating research data into valuable knowledge for diverse stakeholders, including industry leaders, researchers, and policymakers.

The first Webinar titled "Lithium metal anode production methods: State of the Art, challenges, and future perspectives." was held online on the 26th of June 2023. The topics included insights from different cluster members on Lithium's production methods, deposition and protective coatings, anode-less production, and industrial scale production of Lithium metal anodes.

The second webinar titled "Going solid for safer batteries" took place on 12 december 2023 and focused on Solid state Li-Metal batteries towards a circular economy potential.

Next events within the SOLID4B cluster, where ADVAGEN will participate are:

1. AM4BAT Workshop on Stakeholder Engagement. To be hosted on February 1st and 2nd, 2024 at Clayton Hotel Cambridge, UK by Photocentric.

2. SPINMATE hybrid workshop. The tentative title will be “SOLID4B: Scaling up high-energy-density solid-state batteries: A lab-to-pilot perspective”. To be hosted by ABEE on 15th April 2024 in Brussels.

5. Monitoring and impact tracking

In order to review the effectiveness of the ADVAGEN dissemination and communication strategy and measure the extent to which this strategy is meeting the planned objectives (c.f. Table 5 & Table 9), impact tracking will be done. All partners will report the performances of their communication and dissemination activities on the “Dissemination and Communication Actions tracker”, whose template is provided in **Annex 2**. The corresponding Excel file has already been made available to the whole consortium (on the secure project shared folder). The collected information will be compiled and updated for each consortium meeting (hence, every six months). Also, important updates will be made at M18 (D8.4, intermediate update of this DEC plan) and at M48 (D8.5, final update), as well as during all reporting periods.

Based on the conclusions of these updates, corrective measures will be put in place if necessary. In case WP8 concludes that the tools and channels defined in this deliverable do not work properly, the strategy will be revised, and alternative tools introduced.

Conclusion

The DEC plan has been developed to ensure ADVAGEN has the largest impact on the targeted stakeholder audiences and the general public. It has been prepared to organise dissemination, exploitation and communication activities for the entire duration of the project. It is expected that all project partners will be active in creating and stimulating broad, public interest in what it has been achieved.

As the project is in its early stages, it is for now impossible to monitor the impact of the dissemination and communication activities implemented. It will be possible to draw such conclusions when the project is more advanced.

Annex 1 – Graphic charter of the ADVAGEN project

Logo

Construction for a font size 60 pt

Typography: All Round Gothic Medium

All Round Gothic is a font family inspired by classic sans serif fonts. This font is a structured geometric sans, but also creates a futuristic atmosphere by its round letterforms.

What if the logo needs to be smaller than 20px?

If the logo needs to be used in small format - under 20px - it remains in one line.

Protection zone

What you cannot do with this logo

Distortion

Rotation

Put the logo in a box

Change colors and font

Colors

Allowed variations

No color declinaison is allowed except for white logotype on logo's colors background.

Institutional palette

For Graphics, Design & typography . Similare shades are also accepted.

	#5554A4 -> #8AD5EC	R: 85 -> 138 G: 84 -> 213 B: 164 -> 236	C: 78% -> 42% M: 77% -> 0% Y: 0% -> 5% K: 0% -> 0%
	#5554A4	R: 85 G: 84 B: 164	C: 78 M: 77% Y: 0% K: 0%
	#8AD5EC	R: 138 G: 213 B: 236	C: 42% M: 0% Y: 5% K: 0%
	#6AC9CA	R: 106 G: 201 B: 202	C: 55% M: 0% Y: 24% K: 0%

Typography

COPPERPLATE GOTHIC BOLD	Web Headings logo
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	
Calibri Regular	Headings Text
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	
Calibri Italic	Headings Text
<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i>	
Calibri Bold	Headings Text
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	

Stationary

Word document - Title page

Word document - Pages

Word document - headletter

Powerpoint - Title slide

Powerpoint - slides

Stationery set

Annex 2 – Dissemination and Communication Actions tracker

#	Type of PID (repository)	PID of deposited publication	PID (publisher version of record)	Type of publication	Link to publication	Title of the scientific publication	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number	ISSN or e-ISSN	Publisher	Month of publication	Year of publication	Was the publication available	Peer-reviewed?	Book title	Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	Type of publishing venue	Article processing costs that will be charged to the project
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OCeils Files: Data to be completed only if DOI not available

OCeils Files: For book chapter, the title of the chapter, not book

OCeils Files: Data to be completed only if DOI not available

All social media posts related to the ADVAGEN project, whatever the media and the account (personal, company/institution, project account), should be tracked to establish proper use patterns.

#	Purpose of the post	Social media	Partner(s) involved	Date of publication	Total		# of engagement (sharing, likes & comments)	Total funding amount for the activity (€)
					Main type of audience	Estimated # of persons reached		
1	Announce the launch of the ADVAGEN project and its KOM	LinkedIn		19/09/22	Research & Scientific community	0		
2	Announce the launch of the ADVAGEN project and its KOM	Twitter		19/09/22	Press&Media			
3	Present ABEE	LinkedIn		11/08/2022	Research & Scientific community			
4	Present ABEE	Twitter		11/08/2022	Press&Media			
5	Present INEGI	LinkedIn		16/11/22	Research & Scientific community			
6	Present INEGI	Twitter		16/11/22	Press&Media			
7	Present POLITO	LinkedIn		22/11/22	Research & Scientific community			
8	Present POLITO	Twitter		22/11/22	Press&Media			
9								
10								
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This sheet can only be completed by EQY

Period considered						
From	Date	To	Date	representing	X	months

Main results

	Objective	Results	Comment
Number of users per month	300		
Average duration of visits	> 2 min		
Number of visits of the News section	20		

Location of visitors

Country	N° of visitors	%

